

HOW TO IMPROVE ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILLS

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Abstract: This article discusses speaking in a foreign language, whether it belongs to a certain circle or the most useful aspects. Basic technique, classical approach to language learning, lingo-cultural approach, communicative approach, intensive technique, emotional and meaningful test preparation method. You can mix and match integrated methods.

Key words: English communication, listening comprehension, teaching speech, methods, techniques.

INTRODUCTION

As we live in the age of technical and technological development, the demand for skilled personnel who have a deep understanding of their profession and can communicate freely in Russian and English is increasing day by day. One of the most important tasks in the education and training of students is to teach students foreign languages in addition to their mother tongue, and from this point of view, to teach English. In the last few years, learning a foreign language has become a necessity rather than a way of self-development. A foreign language has become a mandatory component of education not only in schools and universities, but also in many additional pre-school educational institutions. The demand for a foreign language in society, on the one hand, as well as parents' understanding that language is not only a factor in the upbringing of a modern person, but also the basis of his social and material well-being in society, on the other hand, make early learning of a foreign language especially popular and relevant. If 20 years ago knowledge of a language was required only in certain fields of work, now it is necessary to master at least one. It is the ability to make the student interested in the English language, to develop his speech in English, and to teach him professional communication. The main goal of developing professional communication in English is to improve students' oral speech in English, to develop the ability to communicate with others. The task of developing speech includes a number of special tasks: 1. Introducing students to the environment, improving their speech, enriching their vocabulary;

2. Formation of the grammatical aspect of speech;
3. Education of sound culture of speech.

The most popular techniques for acquiring speaking skills in English: basic technique, classical approach to language learning, linguistic-cultural approach, communicative approach, intensive technique, emotional and meaningful method of test preparation. The teacher can mix all the above methods and use them in cooperation with language learners. Since the educational technology market is full of offers for the most diverse ways to learn English, every teacher, especially young professionals, must: perfect their technique and definitely succeed.

MAIN PART

In order to achieve any level of excellence that creates a unique style of teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to study the known and most effective method for a long time. The classical approach to learning a foreign language can be on the list of the least effective. At the heart of the classical approach is the understanding of language as a real and correct means of communication, which means that all components of the language - oral and written language, listening, etc. - the student should develop systematically and harmoniously. The classical technique exhausts the language by itself, but this is not a disadvantage. This comprehensive approach is primarily aimed at developing students' ability to understand and create it. The method includes training with an Uzbek teacher and students, but this method of teaching (though not "fashionable") may not be very effective: a non-native teacher should be able to analyze and compare language systems, compare designs, communicate information better, explain grammar rules, and avoid mistakes. Speech is one of the main language activities. Students share information by speaking. Speaking plays an important role in teaching English.

It is impossible to communicate without talking. Speech takes 30 percent of speaking. Speaking in the best means of importing and strengthening, mastering basic linguistic knowledge in English, developing habits and building skills. Students of higher educational institutions will have the opportunity to use English speech units or phrases, words, phrases, sentences. They are actively and constantly destroyed. It is impossible to implement an English as a foreign language program without gradually mastering English phonetic vocabulary and grammar materials. It is recommended to start teaching speech from the first lessons. Teaching speaking is closely related to other speaking activities such as listening comprehension, reading and writing. Teaching speech has its own mechanisms. Without them, speech cannot be taught, organized or taught. They include:

pronunciation sounds, sound combinations, words, phrases, sentences, intonations, accent. Teachers should teach them in advance. Students must pronounce them correctly. Students only focus on the content of the speech if they can use them. Teaching English Speaking, they help the teacher to find easy, effective ways and exercises to teach speaking. They are as follows:

1. Linguistic features and difficulties of teaching speech.
 - a) correctly chooses language materials such as phonetics, lexicon, grammar.
 - b) features, difficulties of the selected phonetic lexicon, forms, meanings, uses of grammatical materials of speech.
 - c) difficulties in correct pronunciation, intonation, accent.
 - d) difficulties in the skills and habits of using sentences correctly.
 - e) Using replication.
2. Additional linguistic features and difficulties of teaching speech.
 - a) addressed to someone, something, directed.
 - b) speaking in situations.
 - c) use of aids and equipment in teaching speech.
 - d) to be motives for teaching speech.
 - e) the condition of teaching speech.
3. Features and difficulties of the psychology of teaching speech
 - a) using monologue and dialogue to teach speech.
 - b) having the need to teach to speak.
 - c) verbal expression of thought.
 - d) memories, etc.

Listening comprehension and speaking are integrated into oral speech or make oral communication. Speech cannot be created without listening and understanding. By listening and getting information, students can respond by speaking. Through listening comprehension, students learn and familiarize themselves with words, phrases, sentences and their pronunciation that are essential for speech. Speech is also related to reading. By reading, students get new information and content. They use information for speech. By reading, students combine and master the pronunciation of words, word combinations, and intonations. For this, you need help to learn to speak. Speech is closely related to writing. Writing helps the memory, the speaker remembers the information. So we can say that speaking helps with listening comprehension, reading and writing. It is impossible to teach, study and learn speech without communication of speech activity. Listening, speaking, reading, and writing complement each other in teaching English. Speech is divided

into monologic, dialogic speeches and polylogous speeches. Monological and dialogic speeches are taught in schools, lyceums, colleges. But polylogical speech is not taught there. Teaching speech has its purpose, content, future of teaching, mechanisms and stages. The goals of teaching speech. Teaching English has its own goals. They are:

Objective 1: To teach speaking as a means of teaching English or as a means of communication in English.

Goal 2: To be able to use speech in the formation of communication or in the formation of speech habits.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, speaking can be a means of communication in English, and speaking itself is taught by speaking. Speech should be taught in order to be able to use it in activities. The teacher should form speech habits. Habits of using speech in speech activity. The requirements of the programs, speech training should be organized according to the requirements of the program. Each institution, school, high school, college and higher education has its own programs and requirements for teaching speech. These requirements for teaching English speaking are written in the programs.

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